

HOLISTIC APPROACH TO REHABILITATION OF SUBSTANDARD MASONRY INFILLED RC FRAMES

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ABSTRACT

This paper examines new sustainable and holistic retrofitting approach combining sustainable materials, structural strengthening, and energy retrofitting. Two masonry walls and two nearly half-scale masonry infilled reinforced concrete frames were tested in out-of-plane bending. The infills were retrofitted using basalt textile reinforced geopolymer mortar integrated with a standard thermal insulation representing a new generation of sustainable advanced composite materials for structures. The tests showed that structural and energy retrofitting have a potential to become an effective system, which can address the structural and thermal deficiencies of buildings in a more comprehensive manner.

KEYWORDS

TRM; masonry infill; RC frame; energy retrofitting; structural retrofitting; geopolymer; metakaolin; basalt textiles; out-of-plane.

INTRODUCTION

Masonry infilled reinforced concrete (RC) frames are systems commonly used in residential building construction of the Southern Europe as well as world-wide. They consist of a primary structural frame, typically made reinforced concrete, with masonry walls filling the spaces between the structural members. The infills are non-structural elements and have been regularly used in the frames of RC buildings mostly due to their relatively low cost. Such structures were built mostly between '60s and '90s with little or no seismic provisions and due to the absence of strict energy performance regulations were not thermally insulated.

When large lateral forces are imposed on the structure, e.g. during the earthquakes, the presence of infills can alter the behaviour of the entire building. At first, the infill walls work in conjunction with the primary structural RC frame to distribute and resist seismic loads, enhancing the overall strength and stiffness of the building. However, the brittle nature of masonry, poor bond to the frames as well as lack of anchorage and proper detailing typically in the OOP (out-of-plane) direction makes such structures vulnerable to collapse (Furtado et al., 2016; Mosalam & Günay 2015). Out-of-plane movements in masonry infills can lead to various issues and concerns, including reduced structural stability, increased risk of collapse, and potential damage to the building envelope or interior finishes. On top of that, many buildings have surpassed their designed lifespan, and their structural elements have deteriorated due to ageing and lack of maintenance, which significantly increases their seismic vulnerability. Ageing of buildings also affects the energy performance and increases energy consumption of the buildings (Pohoryles et al., 2022). Recent reports estimate that buildings are responsible for as much as 35% of the energy consumption and 38% of the CO₂ emissions globally (United Nations Environment Programme, 2020). Current global challenges to reduce the human impact on the environment require immediate actions, therefore, given the scale of the problem it is important to develop new design approaches and procedures, which can address and tackle the two issues simultaneously, in a holistic manner. Such novel approach should also focus on the use of sustainable and durable advanced materials, which can offer additional longevity of the application.

Textile reinforced mortars (TRM) combining open-mesh textiles and binding mortar have shown to be a versatile and robust strengthening solution for masonry infilled reinforced concrete frames (Koutas et al., 2015; Sagar et al., 2019; Koutas & Bournas 2019; Furtado et al., 2021). Recent studies attempted to integrate TRM strengthening with standard thermal insulation and capillary tube systems (Gkournelos

et al., 2019; Bournas, 2018; Baek et al., 2022). However, current retrofitting solutions for masonry infilled walls are often expensive, lead to incompatibility issues, and promote the use of Ordinary Portland Cement-based binders, which production of largely contributes to the global CO₂ emissions (Andrew, 2018). More sustainable binders like geopolymers (Davidovits, 2021) can help to overcome this issue and offer balanced and sustainable approach for retrofitting. Recent studies on geopolymer binders for textiles have proven that such binders can offer similar or even better performance than standard OPC binders (Cholostiakow et al., 2023). This experimental study aims to integrate thermal retrofitting with structural TRM strengthening using a more sustainable type of matrix such as metakaolin-based geopolymer in combination with basalt textiles. As such, the developed system can offer both structural and energy retrofitting by the same time employing advanced durable and sustainable materials. The performance of the retrofitting system was assessed through experimental out-of-plane testing of two masonry walls as well as two 1:2.5 scale masonry infilled RC frames.

TESTING PROGRAMME

The testing programme consisted of two phases. The first phase included out-of-plane tests on simply supported masonry panels, which aimed to integrate structural and energy retrofitting. The second phase consisted of two out-of-plane tests on masonry infilled reinforced concrete frames, which aimed to assess the performance of the system in a more practical case.

Test walls (panels)

In attempt to replicate substandard masonry wall structures, standard hollow clay bricks with nominal dimensions around ~185x90x65 mm were employed. Two single-wythe walls were build keeping the overall dimensions of the wall specimen of about 380x1090 mm (see Figure 1). Normal strength cement-lime-sand mortar was used using the ratio of 1:1:5, respectively. The compressive and flexural strength of the mortar used to build the walls was determined at the day of testing and was equal to 9.8 MPa and 2.0 MPa, respectively.

Figure 1: Test specimens' geometry – masonry wall panels.

The tests on the wall panels aimed to investigate if such integrated system can effectively resist bending forces without losing the composite action between the materials. The same binder was used to bond the insulation and the textiles, thus making it a practical and cost-effective approach. Two different strengthening configurations (Figure 2) were investigated:

- i) wall retrofitted with two layers of TRM serving as a reference.
- ii) wall retrofitted with two layers of TRM with an insulation panel in between (“sandwich application”).

The reference wall was strengthened following standard procedures applying two consecutive TRM layers, one after another, each about 6 mm thick. The wall with thermal insulation was retrofitted in two steps:

Figure 2: Integration of TRM retrofitting with thermal insulation.

At first, one geopolymer TRM layer was applied, and, following that, the EPS panel was bonded to the wall using the same binder that was used for the textiles' matrix, i.e., geopolymer mortar. The insulation panel after bonding was pressed over its entire surface to ensure that the binder between the panel and the masonry is of uniform thickness. In the second phase, after one day of curing the second layer of the TRM was applied on the panel's surface and was left for curing.

The walls were tested as simply supported over a 1000 mm clear span. The load was applied at a constant displacement rate of 0.04 mm/sec. The vertical displacement was measured at the mid-span using two LVDTs, each placed near the wall's edge to account for any rotation during the testing. The rigid motion of the wall was measured using two LVDTs, each placed at the wall's top surface, above the support.

Figure 3: Test specimens' geometry – masonry infilled frames.

Test walls (infilled frames)

Based on the conclusions drawn from the tests on the wall panels two identical 1:2.5 scale masonry infilled RC frames were designed (Figure 3). The RC frame elements comprised 100x160 mm columns and 100x200 mm beam. The main longitudinal reinforcement of the columns consisted of six 8 mm rebars and 6 mm stirrups whereas the beam's reinforcement comprised four 8 mm bars (two at the top and two at the bottom) and 6 mm stirrups. The one-leaf infill was constructed using the same bricks as

were used to build the masonry panes with length reduced to 140 mm for scaling purposes. One of the frames was non-retrofitted and served as a reference. The second infilled frame was retrofitted on the frontal side using the “sandwich” configuration (1 TRM layer + Insulation + 1 TRM layer). The textile retrofitting was applied on the entire frontal surface of the infill and the frame’s elements. As such, the geopolymer TRM overlay spanned between the top of the beam and the top of the concrete base, while the sides were wrapped around the columns at 90° degrees. In the second step, the insulation panels were applied using several EPS panels pinned to the masonry and the frame using standard 6 mm insulation plugs in arrangement depicted in the Figure 4. Finally, the last layer of TRM was applied over the entire area of the EPS panes in the same way as the first layer. The corners of the frame and EPS panels were rounded to avoid unnecessary stress concentration in the TRM overlay at bent corners. The specimen was tested in a rigid steel frame. The base of the frame was anchored to the rigid steel frame using 8 M20 steel bolts, thus preventing any possible uplift during testing. The frame was restrained from the lateral movements using two steel RHS posts placed directly in the corners of the frame (see the cut-off area in the insulation panels in the Figure 4) so as only the infill was designed to resist the lateral load. The lateral load was applied to the central part of the infill using a rigid convex steel plate with the loading area 330x525 mm – dimensions corresponding to about one-third of the infill’s height and width, respectively. A constant displacement rate was maintained in both OOP tests equal to 0.02 mm/sec. The OOP displacement was measured using two LVDTs located in the center of the infill, in the vicinity of the middle horizontal bed joint.

Figure 4: The layout of the EPS panels. Note that brick units are shown just for clarity.

Retrofitting materials

Commercial epoxy-coated basalt textiles were employed as mortar reinforcement (Figure 5). The textile mesh had a balanced yarn distribution across its two orthogonal direction (warp and weft) and nominal mesh size 6x6 mm. The mechanical properties of the textiles are shown in Table 1.

The geopolymer binding mortar was developed at the University of Thessaly's Laboratory of Concrete Technology and Reinforced Concrete Structures. The binder aimed to replace standard binders based on ordinary Portland cement and thus had similar mechanical properties. The dry mix consisted of aggregates with maximum size of 1 mm as well as 6 mm propylene fibers added in amount of 1% per volume. Metakaolin was used as the precursor and potassium silicate as the activator. The compressive and flexural strength of the hardened mortar was determined on the day of testing using three standard 40x40x160 mm prisms. For the wall panels, the compressive and flexural strength of geopolymer mortar were equal to 40.2 and 4.9 MPa, respectively. For the strengthened masonry infill the strength was equal to 42.7 MPa and 5.8 MPa, respectively.

Figure 5: Basalt textile reinforcing mesh.

Standard 30 mm grey EPS (expanded polystyrene insulation) panels with thermal conductivity value of 0.03W/mK were employed in the energy retrofitting application. Such panels are often a typical choice for energy retrofitting interventions in Southern Europe mainly due to the relatively low cost. Usually, two insulation panels are used (2x30 mm) to satisfy the energy retrofitting requirements in residential buildings. Hence, to keep the scale of the testing (1:2.5), only one EPS panel was used. According to the manufacturer, the compressive strength of the panel was equal at least 0.02 MPa and shear modulus at least 1.0 MPa.

Table 1: Mechanical properties of basalt textile.

Type of textile	Basalt
Coating of fibre rovings	Yes
Elastic modulus of dry fibers	89 GPa
Total weight	250 g/m ²
Weight distribution	50-50%
Nominal thickness (main dir.)	0.039 mm
Tensile strength (main dir.)	1540 MPa

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The main test results are presented in Table 2. The effect of the integration of structural and thermal retrofitting systems was evaluated and discussed in terms of relative increase in the OOP capacity between the masonry panel retrofitted only with two TRM layers (REF) and the panel with integrated energy retrofitting. The strengthening efficiency of the masonry infills was determined as a relative increase in the OOP initial stiffness and bending capacity compared between the frame with an URM and holistically retrofitted infilled frame.

Masonry panels

The application of 30 mm EPS insulation panel led to a change in the section properties due to the increased lever arm. Thus, a stiffer response after cracking and a larger bending capacity was expected in the wall where TRM was combined with EPS insulation material. The failure modes and load-deflection responses for the two wall panels are shown in Figure 6 and Figure 7, respectively.

Since the OOP tests on URM panels would have yielded a negligible strength, such tests were not carried out. The reference wall GEO_B2 retrofitted with two layers of basalt mesh embedded in the geopolymer binder developed initial cracking at a load of about 2.0 kN. The wall failed due to the development of diagonal shear crack near the loading point at 5.79 kN showing that even two TRM layers can considerably increase bending resistance of the masonry panel and lead to shear failure through the brick units.

Table 2: Main test results.

Specimen	Layout	Peak OOP load (kN)	OOP displacement at peak (mm)
Masonry panels			
GEO_B2	2 TRM	5.79	14.2
GEO_B1I1	TRM + Ins + TRM	10.8 (86.5%)	21.6 (52.1%)
Infills in RC frame			
REF_IF_OOP_ND	URM	16.3	38.3
STR_IF_OOP_ND	TRM + Ins + TRM	46.0 (182.2%)	24.5 (36%)

Note: The values in parentheses represent relative percentage change with respect to the reference specimen.

Figure 6: Failure modes for masonry panels.

The geopolymer provided full composite action between the masonry wall and the basalt textile thus confirming its value as a binder for commercially used basalt textiles.

The wall having the EPS panel placed between the two TRM layers showed an improved performance. GEO_B1I1 showed similar response to the reference wall at the initial stages of loading without exhibiting any cracking until reaching a load of around 5 kN. After that point, some minor cracks appeared in the bricks and mortar, which led to a slight degradation of the stiffness. This retrofitting scheme exhibited also a full composite action, which allowed the EPS panel to remain bonded to the masonry surface until the failure at a load equal to 10.8 kN, which corresponds to a strength gain of about 86 %. The failure was due to the shear crack developed through the masonry, TRM and the EPS panel without any signs of local debonding.

The experimental results showed that the integration of both retrofitting schemes have well contributed to the OOP load capacity of the masonry and increased the displacement capacity, which can be beneficial in case of structures subjected to seismic actions. The integration of the thermal insulation increased the OOP capacity by additional 86%. The “sandwich” layout enabled the accommodation of about 52 % larger displacement at peak load than it was measured in the counterpart wall with standard TRM retrofitting. Based on these conclusions, this layout was also used to retrofit one of the masonry infilled frames, which is presented in the next section.

Figure 7: Test results – masonry panels.

Infilled frames

The failure patterns for both infilled frames as well as the OOP load-deflection behaviour is shown in the Figures 8 and Figure 9. The reference URM frame exhibited a failure typical for infills subjected to OOP loads, showing a symmetric cracking pattern propagating from the infill's center towards the frame elements (see Figure 9a), confirming the load was well distributed over the infill. The first cracks appeared at a load of about 9.2 kN in the central part of the infill, across the bed joint just above the 5th course and were followed by diagonal step-cracks propagating towards the frame's corners. With the increasing load, the cracks kept opening and more cracks appeared near the wall's diagonals. This was accompanied by a rapid loss of the OOP stiffness and ductile-like response. After reaching the peak load of 16.3 kN and an OOP displacement of 38 mm, the load started to gradually decrease, which was also associated with further crack opening with some new cracks developing through the brick units. The retrofitting with two basalt TRM layers and an EPS panel in the sandwich configuration proved to be an effective holistic solution for URM infilled frames. STR_IF_OOP_ND exhibited considerably larger initial stiffness compared to the reference infill.

Figure 8: Failure patterns – masonry infilled RC frames.

The initial OOP stiffness was estimated as a secant stiffness determined between 0% and 40 % of the peak load and was equal to 2.61 kN/mm for the reference and 7.02 kN/mm for retrofitted frame, which corresponded to an increase of about 169 %. The large increase in the initial stiffness can be attributed to the effective mobilisation of the two TRM layers and full composite action from the onset of loading. Likewise in case of the wall panels with integrated thermal insulation, the cracking load was not clearly

visible on the load-deflection curve, however, some minor diagonal cracks started developing in the back side of the infill at a load of about 37 kN also showing first signs of debonding from the beam surface at the top of the frame. STR_IF_OOP_ND attained its peak OOP capacity at a load of 46.0 kN, which was associated with detachment of the retrofitting system from the concrete beam's substrate and followed by further damage at the back side of the infill. After that point, the TRM retrofitting was effectively anchored only to the columns, and, as such, was working only in one direction. Shortly after about 18 % load drop and further OOP load increase, the outer TRM layer fractured exhibiting a vertical crack in the middle of the infill. It is worth noting that although the outer layer has fractured some residual strength was still maintained suggesting that inner TRM layer was still partially effective in resisting the load.

Figure 9: Test results – masonry infilled RC frames.

CONCLUSIONS

This study analysed experimentally the concept of combining several materials into one composite retrofitting system capable to tackle structural and energy requirements of the substandard masonry infilled RC buildings at once. These materials included cost-effective basalt textiles, metakaolin-based geopolymer mortar, and standard EPS insulation panels. Three wall panels were tested in bending (one with TRM and one with integrated TRM and EPS panel systems). Based on the results, two nearly half scale masonry infilled frames (URM and strengthened with sandwich layout) were built and tested. The experimental results and test observations prove that such novel combination of the materials can be a viable solution for OOP retrofitting of masonry structures including walls and infills. Based on the tests carried out the following conclusions can be drawn:

- The integration of the TRM and EPS retrofitting system led to an additional 86% increase in OOP capacity of the masonry walls.
- Geopolymer mortar showed excellent bond to the basalt grid, the EPS panel and the masonry substrate and hence can be used as a binder for all materials.
- Tests on 1:2.5 scale masonry infilled frames showed that such holistic approach can lead to an 169% increase in initial stiffness and improve the OOP capacity by almost three times.
- No visible signs of damage were detected at the EPS insulation and TRM interface until reaching about 80% of the ultimate load thus reducing the possibility of thermal bridges formation.

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors wish to thank the European Commission for providing the financial support to carry out this study as a part of Marie Skłodowska-Curie funded research project “THORAX - NEXT GENERATION OF ADVANCED COMPOSITE MATERIALS FOR SUSTAINABLE RETROFITTING OF STRUCTURES” (HORIZON 2020, EU grant agreement 892406 <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/892406>).

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.